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Enhancing Ribasim for reservoir operations: validating a new version with Canteen and expanding to the Drammen basin

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The Drammen Basin in Norway offers a unique opportunity to enhance Ribasim, a water resources planning tool developed by Deltares, to better simulate reservoir operations. Ribasim is designed to model the physical behaviour of managed open water systems, utilizing control rules and a prioritized water allocation strategy. This makes it an essential tool for effective water resources management under changing conditions.

Currently, new functionality is added to the Ribasim code enabling rule-based control options (discrete or continuous) as well as control by optimized allocation to simulate complex reservoir behaviour. This work directly supports the objectives of the STARS4Water project (EU Horizon No 101059372), which aims to improve understanding of climate change impacts on water availability and assess vulnerabilities to ecosystems, society, and the economy at the river basin scale.

To validate these new features, we leverage results from the Canteen model, a reservoir operations model used in the United States. Canteen has been applied to a variety of reservoirs, including the Wilson reservoir in Kansas, serving as a benchmark to assess Ribasim's ability to replicate realistic reservoir dynamics.

In parallel with this validation, Ribasim is applied to simulate reservoir behaviour in the Drammen Basin, broadening the tool's scope and ensuring its applicability across diverse geographical contexts. This will enable Ribasim to model water systems with varied operational and management strategies.

Ultimately, this project seeks to enhance Ribasim's ability to simulate reservoir operations, improving water resources planning and management and ensure efficient water allocation.